

Tape Data Challenge 2021

1. Objectives

The objective of this test is the validation of the maximum tape bandwidth needed for reads and writes to WLCG tape sites. This will imply a realistic RUN 3 load from DAQ systems, experiment T0 activity and exports.

Due to Tier0 having done its own data challenge in June 2021, also still waiting for all the hardware to come, the 2021 Tape Challenge is mainly focused on Tier1 sites for all experiments.

Before the challenge, every experiment provided their estimation on the expected tape throughput for Run3, which are collected in tables 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4, followed by two summary tables covering the overall tape throughput expected for Run3 for Tier0 and Tier1s (tables 1.5 and 1.6).

WLCG operations team also conducted a survey on all tape sites (Tier0 and Tier1s), for their participation of the tape challenge, as well as the available tape resources and configuration. All the site inputs are collected here :

<https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/LCG/TapeTestsPreparation>

1.1 Experiments Objectives

Table 1.1 – ALICE objectives for RUN3

Indicate in this table, the bandwidths required per Tier0 and Tier1s for reads and writes during data taking (DT) and right after data taking(A-DT). In case that you do not use those sites, please put None.

Site	Reads (DT) GB/s	Writes (DT) GB/s	Reads (A-DT) GB/s	Writes (A-DT) GB/s	Transfer rates in data challenge GB/s
CERN	-	5	2	10	15
Total T1s	-	2.8	1.1	2.8	
BNL	None	None	None	None	
CNAF	-	0.8	0.3	0.8	1.0
FNAL	None	None	None	None	
IN2P3	-	0.4	0.1	0.4	0.54
JINR	None	None	None	None	
KISTI	-	0.15	0.1	0.15	0.17
KIT	-	0.6	0.3	0.6	0.53
NDGF	-	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.3
NLT1	-	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.12
RRC-KI	-	0.4	0.1	0.4	0.6
PIC	None	None	None	None	
RAL	-	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.23
TRIUMF	None	None	None	None	

Comments:

- Read rates from tape will be low during Run3 and will be at the level of write rates during LS3, therefore for ALICE the challenge should consider only the write rates.
- ALICE presentation - tape rates:

https://indico.cern.ch/event/1020133/contributions/4281710/attachments/2213250/3746244/ALICE_tapes_Run3_DOMA.pdf

Table 1.2 – ATLAS objectives for RUN3

Indicate in this table, the bandwidths required per Tier0 and Tier1s for reads and writes during data taking (DT) and right after data taking(A-DT). In case that you do not use those sites, please put None.

Site	Reads (DT) GB/s	Writes (DT) GB/s	Reads (A-DT) GB/s	Writes (A-DT) GB/s	participation in the October tape challenge
CERN	No reprocessing during data taking	10GB/s (RAW + AOD)	If reprocessing and all activity read from CTA: 12GB/s	-	
all T1s (avg)	2.5	9.6	8.4	5.1	
BNL	0.6	2.2	1.9	1.2	Yes
CNAF	0.2	0.9	0.8	0.5	Yes
FNAL	None	None	None	None	None
IN2P3	0.4	1.4	1.2	0.7	Yes
JINR	None	None	None	None	None
KISTI	None	None	None	None	None
KIT	0.3	1.2	1.0	0.6	Yes
NDGF	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.3	Yes
NLT1	0.2	0.7	0.6	0.4	Yes
RRC-KI	0	0	0	0	Yes
PIC	0.1	0.4	0.3	0.2	Yes
RAL	0.4	1.4	1.2	0.7	Yes
TRIUMF	0.3	1.0	0.8	0.5	Yes

Comments:

- Maximum throughput for reads after data taking (during reprocessing) if everything (RAW + AOD) comes from CTA: needs to be 8GB/sec RAW, 2GB/sec AOD to Tier-1s, 2GB/sec AOD to Tier-2s - > 12GB/s + grid activity.
 - Grid activity depends on the workflows
- Tier-1s and Tier-2s writes: 4GB/sec in total for Tier-1s & Tier-2s for RAW + AOD export
 - The load is spread according to the MoU share for ATLAS.
 - Extra grid activity should be considered

Table 1.3 – CMS objectives for RUN3:

Indicate in this table, the bandwidths required per Tier0 and Tier1s for reads and writes during data taking (DT) and right after data taking(A-DT). In case that you do not use those sites, please put None.

Site	Reads (DT) GB/s	Writes (DT) GB/s	Reads (A-DT) GB/s	Writes (A-DT) GB/s	participation in the October tape challenge
CERN	TBD	10 (12 during HI run)	12	TBD	
BNL	None	None	None	None	
CNAF	.1	1.2	1.9	.2	
FNAL	.2	2.3	3.7	.4	
IN2P3	.1	0.9	1.5	.1	
JINR	.1	0.9	1.5	.1	
KISTI	None	None	None	None	
KIT	.1	0.9	1.5	.1	YES
NDGF	None	None	None	None	
NLT1	None	None	None	None	
RRC-KI	None	None	None	None	
PIC	.1	0.5	0.7	.1	YES
RAL	.1	0.9	1.5	.1	
TRIUMF	None	None	None	None	

Comments:

- These are estimates that include a safety margin to allow for an imbalance of how sites are used vs their total capacity: resource fraction + min(+10% fraction, resource_fraction) Monitoring the FTS transfers: <https://tinyurl.com/xvnanxn6>

Table 1.4 – LHCb objectives for RUN3:

Indicate in this table, the bandwidths required per Tier0 and Tier1s for reads and writes during data taking (DT) and right after data taking(A-DT). In case that you do not use those sites, please put None.

Site	Reads (DT) GB/s	Writes (DT) GB/s	Reads (A-DT) GB/s	Writes (A-DT) GB/s	participation in the October tape challenge
CERN		5.50	4.24		
BNL	None	None	None	None	
CNAF		2.24	0.86		YES
FNAL	None	None	None	None	
IN2P3		1.26	0.49		YES
JINR	None	None	None	None	
KISTI	None	None	None	None	
KIT	None	2.24	None	None	Yes
NDGF					
NLT1		0.88	0.34		YES
RRC-KI		0.88	0.34		YES
PIC		0.58	0.23		YES
RAL		2.92	1.12		YES
TRIUMF	None	None	None	None	

Comments:

Notice these are minimum bandwidths.

- Shares based on current distribution of the Run 1 + Run 2 RAW data.
- Write BW slightly off: 5.2 GB/s at CERN, 0.3 GB/s to be shared by T1s
- Make the assumption of an LHC duty cycle of 50%, so in practice, the instantaneous write are multiplied by 2

1.2 Sites Objectives

Table 1.5 – Overall CERN objectives for RUN3:

Indicate in this table, the bandwidths required for CERN for reads and writes during data taking (DT) and right after data taking(A-DT).

VO	Reads (DT) GB/s	Writes (DT) GB/s	Reads (A-DT) GB/s	Writes (A-DT) GB/s
ALICE	0	5	2	10
ATLAS	0	10	12	0
CMS	TBD	10	12	TBD
LHCb		5.5	4.24	
Total		30.5	30.24	10

Table 1.6 – Overall T1s objectives for RUN3:

Indicate in this table, the bandwidths required for all T1s for reads and writes during data taking (DT) and right after data taking(A-DT).

VO	Reads (DT) GB/s	Writes (DT) GB/s	Reads (A-DT) GB/s	Writes (A-DT) GB/s
ALICE	0	2.8	1.1	2.8
ATLAS	2.5	9.6	8.4	5.1
CMS	0.8	7.6	12.3	1.1
LHCb		11	3.38	
Total	3.3	31	25.18	9.0

2. Tests driven by experiments

Since tape workflow is tightly integrated into the experiment production system, the tape challenge is not managed centrally. Instead, all four experiments ran their own tape read and/or tape write tests, based on their own needs, driven by the experiment's production workflow and data management systems. In this tape challenge, ATLAS and CMS ran tape write and tape read tests, in both DT and A-DT modes. ALICE and LHCb ran only T0 export to T1s test, ie. tape write tests.

Figure 2.1 shows diagrams of the workflow involved in tape traffic for the four LHC experiments. As one can see, there are common components among them, for example, FTS is used by three experiments (ATLAS, CMS and LHCb) for managing file transfers among Tier0, Tier1 and Tier2 sites. And both ATLAS and CMS use Rucio as their data management system. These shared components also make it possible to build a central Data Challenge monitoring dashboard based on limited data sources like FTS.

Figure 2.1 Diagram of the workflows in tape challenge for four LHC experiments

In order to orchestrate the different test scenarios, we decided to have a “shared clock” among all experiments, as shown in Table 2.1. Basically, the first 2 days were for the DT mode, and the remaining 3 days for the A-DT mode.

Table 2.1 – Timeline of the tape challenge week (October 11~15, 2021) for each experiment (all time are CEST)

VO name	start time (DT mode)	switch from DT to A-DT mode	end time
ALICE	10 am, Monday	Same rates	5PM Friday
ATLAS	10 am, Monday	10PM Tuesday stop new T0 export requests; 10AM Wed, start A-DT mode	5PM Friday
CMS	10 am, Monday	10PM Tuesday stop new T0 export requests. Start with Staging requests Tuesday 10pm-Thursday 10am, then writing	
LHCb	10 am, Monday	None	Whenever everything is transferred

The validation of these tests should be carried out by the different experiments representatives

ALICE: Latchezar Betev, Costin Grigoras

ATLAS: Alessandro Di Girolamo, Mario Lassnig, David Cameron.

CMS: Danilo Piparo, James Robert Letts, Lisa Paspalaki, Benedikt Maier

LHCb: Concezio Bozzi, Chris Haen

3. Test results

Below we will go through results for each experiment, summarize feedback from sites and lessons learned.

3.1 Experiment results

3.1.1 ALICE

ALICE tested T0 export to T1 tape, in both data-taking (DT) and after-data-taking (A-DT) mode. It went smoothly, no particular issues found, all elements in the transfer chain performed as expected. The target rates were achieved, even exceeded, as shown by Figure 3.1.1.1 and Table 3.1.1.1.

Figure 3.1.1.1 – ALICE tape write rate during tape challenge

T1 Centre	Target rate GB/s	Achieved rate GB/s
CNAF	0.8	0.94 (116%)
IN2P3	0.4	0.54 (130%)
KISTI	0.15	0.16 (106%)
GridKA	0.6	0.76 (123%)
NDGF	0.3	0.47 (144%)
NL-T1	0.08	0.1 (122%)
RRC-KI	0.4	0.53 (128%)
RAL	0.08	0.17 (172%)

Sum 2.81GB/s

Table 3.1.1.1 – ALICE tape write rate to each T1 center during the tape challenge

3.1.2 ATLAS

ATLAS exercised both DT and A-DT mode. And in each mode, both tape write and tape read were tested, against the Run3 target rates. The tests went smoothly, following the plan.

T0 export is the main activity during the DT mode. ATLAS developed a machinery to inject data from T0 disk to each T1 tape at a fixed flat rate expected in Run3, as shown by Figure 3.1.2.1, in which the horizontal line represents the target write rate to T1 tape during DT time. For A-DT, the write rate is expected to drop by half, which is also achieved, as shown by Figure 3.1.2.1. Between DT and A-DT modes, in early October 13th, ATLAS intentionally paused tape writing, so as to give sites time to absorb existing requests and get ready for the next A-DT mode.

A-DT mode is dominated by tape staging. The staging requests during this period were all real production requests, from the ongoing Run2 reprocessing and derivation campaigns, run by ATLAS Data Carousel. As shown by figure 3.1.2.2, the overall ATLAS target staging rate was achieved in the DT mode. As for individual sites, depending on the real production needs at the time, some T1s got more requests than the other.

Figure 3.1.2.1 The ATLAS write rate to T1 tape during the tape challenge

Figure 3.1.2.2 The ATLAS read rate from T1 tape during the tape challenge

3.1.3 CMS

CMS tested both tape write and tape read.

Figure 3.1.3.1 shows the CMS tape write rate. CMS has a target write rate (to T1s) of 7.6GB/s in DT mode. This rate consists of two parts, one is the T0 export, another is writing MC production outputs to tape. The target rate for T0 export is 4.2GB/s, which was reached by the T0 export test in the tape challenge. Since there was basically no production traffic during the week, the overall write rate was not reached. Right after the tape challenge week, CMS organized its own tape write test, writing from T1 disk to T1 tape, to measure the max tape write capacity at various sites.

Figure 3.1.3.1 CMS tape write rate in tape challenge

In the tape read test, CMS tried to stage containers of 300TB data from each T1, with the goal of testing the site limit in staging capacity, not particularly targeting at the Run3 rate. Figure 3.1.3.2 shows the CMS tape read rate. Several sites, e.g. KIT, PIC, IN2P3 reached better staging rates compared with previous (the Spring) tape tests.

Figure 3.1.3.2 CMS tape read rate in tape challenge

3.1.4 LHCb

LHCb tested T0 export to T1 tape. The expected tape write rate (to all T1s) is 11GB/s for LHCb during DT. Note that, there were LHCb production staging activities ongoing in parallel to the tape challenge.

Figure 3.1.4.1 shows the LHCb tape write rate. It had a slow start due to several reasons:

- FTS configuration settings, e.g. transfer limits per link and storage, were left at default level at the beginning of the challenge, too low for the test scale;
- LHCb started the challenge with 3 Gridftp gateways at CERN EOS, which was not enough to push for the target rate;
- There were some misunderstanding of the target rate for LHCb, which led to site not allocating enough tape drives early in the challenge.

After all the above issues were fixed, LHCb was able to push the rate much higher, close to the target.

Figure 3.1.4.1 LHCb tape write rate in tape challenge

Along the way, a couple of issues, e.g. link limit not being respected and single Gridftp door assigned all the transfers, were encountered in the LHCb run, which have been brought up to experts' attention.

3.2 T1 Sites

Many T1s shared their observations and experience[1][2], which gave invaluable information on how the tape storage systems themselves performed in the tape challenge.

All T1s are proactively prepared for the tape challenge, making sure enough tape resources are in place to meet the expected rates from all experiments. This challenge also gave some T1s a good opportunity to test and tune their newly deployed tape system.

From T1's point of view, tape resources were not really stressed in this challenge. This is partially because some experiments aimed to reach the target Run3 tape rates instead of stressing tapes, partially because experiments didn't keep a sustained rate to all sites. In the cases where experiment pressure was high, all but one site see no problem meeting the requirements.

Sites also gave suggestions and feedback on topics like how to run a tape challenge effectively and what are the optimal ways of utilizing tape resources, which we will cover in the next section "lessons learned".

4. Lessons learned and recommendations

4.1 Orchestration of the tape challenge among all experiments

In this tape challenge, it's completely in the experiment's control on how to organize and run their tests, based on their real needs and workflow/data management systems.

Experiments agreed upon a "shared clock" beforehand. That is, the first two days of the week will be the DT mode, and the last 3 days for the A-DT mode. In reality, this "shared clock" helped only partially to synchronize tests among experiments. One thing we missed is for all experiments to reach peak, either for write or for read, at the same time. This limited our ability to really stress tape resources.

In future challenges, a proactive sharing of technical details among experiment expert teams during the preparation phase may help in orchestrating all experiments to move in full-sync.

Another lesson learned is that one week appears to be too short for testing a complicated infrastructure like the tape system across 4 experiments and more than 10 T1 sites. The warm-up phase, ie. system tuning on both experiments side and site side, takes quite some time, for all to reach the target condition. ALICE had a mock run with sites a week before, which helped them to have a very smooth run during the tape challenge week.

Sites also have some concrete suggestions on running a tape challenge. One suggestion is that if experiments plan to use fake data in a tape write test, coordination between experiments and sites is needed to make sure the fake data are kept separate from real data on tapes, so it will be easier for sites to reclaim tape space afterwards. Another suggestion is that experiments had better use different data samples for write and read tests, because cleaning data from the disk buffer takes time, it's very convenient to do on the fly during the challenge.

4.2 Monitoring

4.2.1 Central monitoring

The Data Challenge dashboard, which covers both the network challenge and tape challenge parts, has proved to be very useful in monitoring the overall picture of how WLCG tape resources are being used by all experiments, and by what activities. Such information is not available on experiment specific dashboards. Further improvements are needed, with priority being to have a consistent representation of the experiment's data, and to cover all traffic, including XRootD traffic.

4.2.2 Site monitoring

We are still very limited in this area, only four T1s provided their site tape monitoring links. As valuable as the site feedback is for optimal utilization of tape resources, we need to improve our monitoring on site tape systems.

One issue reported from sites is that, usually tape resources are shared among all experiments, sometimes even with non-LHC communities. Even for the same experiment, locally initiated activities and experiment initiated activities are run on the same tape system. To report the correct information, effort from sites will be needed to distinguish the different experiments and activities on their local monitoring, before making them public. A good example here is the KIT tape monitoring.

In the meantime, another suggestion is for WLCG to put effort on integrating site tape activities information into the central MONIT. The now-finished WLCG archival storage WG established a tape metrics infrastructure, in which sites periodically update a local json file with relevant tape activities information. The json file is then pulled into WLCG MONIT, from where further data aggregation and visualization can be done using the existing infrastructure. This WLCG tape metrics infrastructure may be a good starting point, to work towards a central monitoring with site information integrated.

4.3 Optimal use of tape resources

To face the storage challenge of the HL-LHC, tape resources are expected to play a more crucial role in experiment workflow. Therefore, to explore the optimal way of utilizing tape resources has become an important topic. This requires a close collaboration between experiments and sites, and any effort spent here will also benefit both in the end.

In the tape challenge, many sites shared their experience and plans on how to optimally utilize the tape systems.

The BNL feedback summarizes the general principles on how to extract max tape drive read performance. It starts with writing (so called “smart writing”), ie. to co-locate files on tape based on their recall pattern, either by datasets or by other units in which files will be recalled. The goal is to reduce the time spent on tape head repositioning (seek time) and the number of tape remounts. To achieve this goal, efforts from the experiments are also needed, in order to fully utilize the “smart writing” features provided by the site.

The FNAL feedback emphasizes on the importance of more performant disk buffer hardware in front of tape, so to make sure disk I/O is not the bottleneck in terms of fully utilizing the tape bandwidth.

Several sites report better tape performance by some experiments than others, due to file size difference. Bigger files leads to better tape bandwidth utilization, for both migration and staging.

There are many other good experiences from sites, which we won't cover them all here. Please refer to the site talks for more details.

4.4 Other observations and suggestions

4.4.1 srm+https in future challenges

In this tape challenge, srm+gridftp protocol is used for tape access, because that's what most production tape systems currently use. As WLCG is moving in the direction of deprecating globus/gridftp, Run3 is expected to work with the new srm+https protocol, which we should use in future tape challenges.

4.4.2 site staging profile

The site staging profile, used by the ATLAS Data Carousel, is found to be useful by sites. Other experiments may consider adopting it. This profile allows sites to tell experiments how to submit staging requests in bulk mode, by defining the site recall limits.

This profile is configurable in the WLCG CRIC. Of course, in order to use it, experiment workflow and data management systems need to evolve to integrate this profile, ie. to respect the limits defined in it in production.

5. Summary

Overall, this tape challenge was a very fruitful exercise. All experiments and all T1 sites participated, first of its kind. It presented an opportunity to exercise the tape workflows at the

Run3 scale for all LHC experiments. Not all experiments reached their desired throughput on all aspects, but both experiments and sites now have a better idea what to expect in Run3 in terms of tape usage. More importantly, lessons learned from this exercise will benefit us all in future challenges, and Run3 and beyond.

For the next tape challenge, we target for a longer period (2 weeks), in the first quarter of next year, in combination with Tier0 commissioning tests.

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